

Systematic review of value types in academic literature

Step by step instructions to guide systematic review of peer reviewed papers by contributing authors

Assessment Statements

In this task, we are seeking evidence from the peer-reviewed literature to support the following assessment statements (subject to refinement based on the evidence we collate). In July we will conduct a similar assessment of environmental policy documents.

- Diversity of worldviews is associated with value plurality, and with different ways of relating to nature and making decisions about how to use and/or manage natural resources
- Environmental policy documents present various frameworks for organising human-nature relationships, each reflecting different types of values. However, most frameworks have emphasised different forms of instrumental and intrinsic values. Various types of relational values presented in the wider scientific literature have received less attention
- Inclusion of relational values and associated language in environmental policy can improve biodiversity conservation and human-environmental well-being, and gives comprehensive information for policy outcomes, especially with respect to addressing environmental conflicts
- The ways in which environmental issues are discussed and presented influences the types of values that are formed or elicited in society, and the types of legal frameworks and policy responses to global challenges
- Not all values are treated equally in environmental policy. Some knowledge systems and associated values have been prioritized, while others have been obscured, leading to conflicts and problems of environmental and epistemic injustice

Instructions

Please use these instructions as a guide to carrying out your review on those papers.

We will all use a google sheet to collect our results.

Here is a [link](#) to 30 papers for you to review by the **29th June 2020** corresponding to the IDs aligned with your names in above sheet

General note: We're interested in knowing whether the topics below are explicitly mentioned or implied. We ask that you copy explicit text (and use double quotation marks, because Excel reads only

one quotation mark as a marker that the cell contains text, and will omit it in most views) and summarize/describe implicit references without quotes.

- 1) Write down the location of the **institution** of the **first author** and the **name of the institution**
- 2) Clarify whether the paper discusses values as **monistic** (values can be integrated into a single unit, **dualistic** (e.g., considers two irreducible elements or modes of values) or **pluralistic** (recognises multiple irreducible elements or modes of values)
- 3) **Policy relevance** - summarise what the authors describe as the policy relevance or implications of their findings. Special attention should be given to core International Policies such as SDGs/ Agenda 2030, CBD, multilateral trade agreements, etc
- 4) State the **Global Challenge** (GC) considered in the assessment. i.e.
 - a) GC1: Rapid and/or large-scale land use transformations (choosing among the following: large infrastructure projects such as dams, mining, large monoculture plantations, rapid urbanization processes)
 - b) GC2: Agriculture and food production (intensive vs. extensive, monoculture vs. agroecological, large scale vs. small farmers, corporations vs. IPLCs)
 - c) GC3: Unsustainable fisheries (small scale/artisanal vs. industrial, aquaculture vs. coastal/oceans) (
 - d) GC4: "Fence and forget" or the use of protected areas for biodiversity conservation
- 5) **Targeted Policy Themes** (TPT) considered in the assessment. i.e.
 - a) TPT1. Diversity of values of nature and grassroots environmental movements.
 - b) TPT2. Incorporation of the multiple values of nature into public and corporate accounting.
 - c) TPT3. Diversity of values of nature in education for the future. The role of education (with emphasis on young people) for catalyzing multiple values inter-generationally
 - d) TPT4. Mainstreaming diverse values of nature in policies across ministries.
- 6) We are looking for **expressions of value**, corresponding to the three value types – intrinsic, instrumental and relational value
 - a) Read each article to determine if instrumental, relational and intrinsic values have been defined or described (Yes/No)
 - b) If yes, in 1-2 sentences describe how the authors justify each value type.
 - c) Copy and paste over the definition if provided.

- d) In some papers the conceptualisation of value may be implicit. Implicit is when it's pretty clear what the type of value is, but that's not directly stated. For example: "preserving local species supports human wellbeing" (instrumental) – unless the context suggests otherwise (for example, well being is defined as the identity of a community or the 'support' function is used to stress the dependency upon local species for survival).
 - e) If the definition or description of value is unclear then please code as 'unclear'.
 - f) If no definition or description is provided then please code as 'unspecified'
- 7) We are looking for **prominent ecosystem valuation concepts** such as ecosystem services, natural capital, Nature Contributions to People etc. Please code.
- 8) We are looking for **knowledge systems** in the following 2 ways
- a) Indigenous and/or local knowledge
 - b) Other non-Western, non-codified, non-"mainstream" way of thinking about knowledge or obtaining knowledge (please describe)
- 9) In what ways is this knowledge being represented in the policy recommendations? Please describe if there any references to how this knowledge is used or constrained in policy.
- 10) We are looking at other ways that **human-nature relationships (HNR)** are explicitly described in text (e.g., connection to nature, human-nature relatedness, biocultural diversity, sacred landscapes)
- 11) We are looking for **HNR that are expressed/implied in worldviews or philosophies**. So far, in the literature we identified the following examples, but others might come from the analysis of the papers.:
- a) Biocentric: intrinsic value of living organisms and/or general view that consider life valuable
 - b) Ecocentric: intrinsic value of collectives (species and ecosystems) and/or general view that consider the importance of a systemic view rather than the value of single things
 - c) Anthropocentric: in the sense of narrow/strong anthropocentrism ('human centric,' this worldview entails human superiority in relation to other species) and/or in a wider sense as weak or relational anthropocentrism (this refers to approaches that still focus on human perspectives, but are not limited to a narrow and instrumental understanding of the relations between people and environments/nature (Norton 1984). In this perspective aesthetic dimensions, embeddedness, dependency, reliance on natural processes are also addressed. The narrative is not one of mastery, but of dependence and stewardship. This sometimes includes a focus on communities, relationships of care and reciprocal responsibilities, but still focuses on human communities at the (porous) center of analysis. It can overlap with other understandings

- d) Pluricentric/ Non centric/ non dualist/ relational approaches: focus is on relationships between humans and more than human others and systemic processes that might be addressed as for example, reciprocal, interdependent, sometimes equal, intertwined, embedded, and more... In general, there is not one center (neither human nor other beings), but a network-like image of inter-relations. Different or all value types can be used with respect to different types of relationships and overlap.
- e) Others... Other world views that appear in the paper (please describe)

12) Is the paper an **empirical study** (drawing upon their own data), review or perspective?

13) Does the paper suggest that some **value types/ways of knowing are being obscured or neglected**? If explicit, please quote. If implicit, please describe

14) Does the paper discuss the way in which **institutions prioritise the elicitation or solicitation of values**? Please copy text if explicit. Please describe if implicit.

Key concepts

Instrumental value:

Instrumental values are associated with living and non-living entities, as means to achieve human ends or satisfy human preferences (Pascual *et al.*, 2017a). Applied to natural entities or ecosystems, instrumental valuation considers these to provide utility for human beings (Chan *et al.*, 2016; Eser *et al.*, 2014; Rolston, 1994; Weston, 1985).

Instrumental values are (at least in principle) substitutable by other means without loss. Instrumental values are useful when people articulate what matters to them in the language of means-ends relationships. Sample instrumental justifications in European biodiversity strategies often feature self-interest/best interest language (e.g. Eser *et al.* 2014).

Instrumental values are commonly thought to be assessed through economic (*e.g.*, monetary) and non-economic (*e.g.*, ecological) indicators.

Ecosystem services as instrumental:

Ecosystem services are commonly thought to be instrumental, This has led to criticisms of turning nature into a means to human ends, which does not cater for the different ways that people perceive and relate to nature (*e.g.*, Norgaard, 2010; Raymond *et al.*, 2013; Spash, 2008) (Chan *et al.*, 2012). However, ES are not necessarily instrumental: cultural ES are often associated with relational values, but provisioning, regulating and supporting ES can also be associated with relational values when they are not deemed to be substitutable.

Natural capital approaches may be instrumental if supported by the weak sustainability paradigm common to environmental economics; but could reflect intrinsic and relational values if supported by strong sustainability approaches (see Neumayer 2010 for these paradigms).

From the perspective of instrumental values, welfare/wellbeing tend to refer to preference-based utility, and to economic indicators of welfare such as GDP.

Intrinsic values:

Intrinsic values refer to entities or processes that are worth protecting as ends in-and-of themselves (Batavia & Nelson, 2017; Regan, 1986; Rolston, 1994; Taylor, 1986) independently of direct reference to human valuing (O'Connor & Kenter 2019; O'Neill 1993) or both (Díaz *et al.*, 2015; Pascual *et al.*, 2017a). This is broader than the understanding of intrinsic value in previous iterations of the IPBES framework, which consider the value of an entity independent of how it relates to humans (Pascual *et al.*, 2017b).

The key is to recognise intrinsic values in the reason why something is valued, as in: for its own sake, regardless of a relationship to human beings (Himes & Muraca, 2018a).

Intrinsic values are often thought to be assessed through biophysical indicators such as abundance and endemism, but can also be articulated by people (Callicott, 2003). Intrinsic values may also be reflected in appeals to the interests, consequences to or rights of non-human nature without reference to people as valuers (O'Connor & Kenter, 2019). However, we are considering subjective articulations that refer to human values (e.g. experiencing wonder) as relational, rather than intrinsic values (see below).

In the literature aesthetic or eudaemonic values are often also referred to as intrinsic values (to mean that something is valued as is, not for what it serves or delivers, and that it is considered not substitutable). In our classification this falls under relational-eudaemonic and needs to be identified clearly.

Relational values:

Relational values are explicitly *non-instrumental* human-nature-relationships (Chan *et al.*, 2018; Díaz *et al.*, 2015; Himes & Muraca, 2018a; Jax *et al.*, 2013; Muraca, 2011, 2016b), which are in principle non-substitutable, and which lose their meaning if treated as merely instrumental values (Arias Arévalo *et al.*, 2017; Himes & Muraca, 2018a; Jax *et al.*, 2013; Klain *et al.*, 2017). An example is friendship, which is destroyed if reduced to a means to an end (O'Neill *et al.*, 2008). Relational values differ from intrinsic values since the latter are defined as independent of relationships with people.

Relational values were introduced to the ecosystem management literature to better capture the complex ways in which people express their relationship to 'nature' (Arias-Arévalo *et al.*, 2018; Arias Arévalo *et al.*, 2017; Chan *et al.*, 2016) building on contributions on relational values in philosophy (Muraca, 2019.)

They can refer to different types of relationships or value domains, for example (based on Arias Arévalo *et al.*): all systems of relations and processes that are conditions to protect the life supporting system or those that contribute to ecological resilience. all systems of relations and processes that are conditions that allow people to define themselves and provide sense to their existence Or in other words, those conditions necessary for enhancing social resilience fundamental/ constitutive). See Tables for guidance in search of terms:

Table 2. Classification of ecosystem services values across different metaphors of human-nature relationships.

Metaphors of human-nature relationship	Value Domain	Articulated values	Definition	Examples of valued ecosystem services†
Gaining from nature	<i>Instrumental</i> Ecosystems and biodiversity seen as merely a means to achieve utility	Monetary value	Biodiversity and ecosystems contributions to utility, which are measured through prices	Erosion protection Fibres, fuel and other raw materials Genetic material Biochemical species and/or resources Ornamental resources
Living for nature	<i>Intrinsic</i> Biodiversity and ecosystems have value in themselves	Moral duties towards nature	Moral duties towards biodiversity and ecosystems	Nursery habitat Genepool protection
Living in nature	<i>Fundamental</i> Conditions to i) protect the life supporting system, ii) allow people to define themselves, and iii) provide sense to their existence.	Ecological resilience	The capacity of ecosystems of maintaining their integrity in face of disturbance	Climate regulation Water regulation Soil formation and regeneration Biological regulation
		Livelihood, subsistence	Critical ES to achieve livelihood goals	Food Water
		Mental and physical health	Physical benefits perceived from ecosystems' regulation of water, air and diseases; and mental benefits due to nature exposure	Air quality regulation Natural hazard mitigation Waste treatment Opportunities for recreation and ecotourism
		Identity	Biodiversity and ecosystems are considered references to determine people's sense of personal and social identity	Cultural heritage and identity
		Cultural heritage	Landscape's tangible and intangible features which are historically significant (e.g., buildings monuments, traditions, stories, traditional ecological knowledge, other knowledge systems).	Cultural heritage and identity

<i>Endaimonistic</i> Entities and processes which represent conditions for leading a 'good human life'	Sacredness	Spiritual, religious or sacred attachment to biodiversity and ecosystems	Spiritual and religious inspiration
	Symbolic value	Meanings associated to ecosystems. These meanings are conceived to be inseparable of the represented ecosystems but are also valuable in themselves	Cultural heritage and identity
	Social cohesion	Human uses of biodiversity and ecosystems as a context for social cohesion enhancement	Opportunities for enhancing social relations
	Sense of place	Emotional attachment to a place (feelings of belonging, commitment, identity or community)	Cultural heritage and identity
	Meaningful occupation	Occupations related to biodiversity and ecosystems that allow people to fulfil a 'good human life'	Cultural heritage and identity
	Aesthetic value	Appreciation of the beauty of nature, grounded on sensations and emotions.	Opportunities for aesthetic appreciation
	Recreational, leisure	Appreciation of tourism, recreational and leisure activities in natural areas	Opportunities for recreation and ecotourism
	Cognitive development,	Appreciation of ecosystems' features within special educational and scientific interest	Opportunities for education and science
	Inspiration	Appreciation of the inspirational values of ecosystems' features	Opportunities for inspiration for culture, art, design
	Environmental justice	Biodiversity, ecosystems or ES are matters of concern within a human rights or a justice context	All ecosystem services
Altruism	Concern for biodiversity, ecosystems or ES in favour of a present larger community (intra-generational) or future generations (inter-generational)	All ecosystem services	

Multiple values: these value categories are defined as mutually exclusive (i.e. in the above definitions, intrinsic and relational values are non-instrumental, and intrinsic values are non-relational), but the values themselves are not mutually exclusive: things can be valuable for instrumental, relational and/or intrinsic reasons at the same time.. As recognized by IPBES (2015) and Pascual *et al.*, (2017), the ways by which people justify the importance of human-nature relationships often overlap. How something is valued depends not only on its characteristics, but the ways in which people relate to it or what they seek to obtain, which depends on the context and value articulating institutions involved (Himes & Muraca, 2018a). For example, food may at the same time have instrumental and relational value depending on the context of meaning and on the local practices that govern the interactions with it (Whyte, 2018a, 2018c; Whyte, 2018).

Worldview: Worldviews are defined by the connections between networks of concepts and systems of knowledge, values, norms and beliefs. Individual person's worldviews are moulded by the community the person belongs to. Practices are embedded in worldviews and are intrinsically part of them (e.g. through rituals, institutional regimes, social organization, but also in environmental policies, in development choices, etc.).

Knowledge system: A knowledge system is a body of propositions that are adhered to, whether formally or informally, and are routinely used to claim truth. A prominent contrast may be between indigenous and local knowledge systems (ILK) and knowledge systems in the natural and social sciences. Knowledge systems (a) generate and represent content, components, classes, or types of knowledge, that are (b) domain-specific or characterized by domain-relevant features as defined by the user or consumer, (c) reinforced by logical relationships that connect the content of knowledge to its value, (d) enhanced by a set of iterative processes that enable the evolution, revision, adaptation, and advances, and (e) are subject to criteria of relevance, reliability, and quality.